

Women's Studies International Forum

Two decades of Theorising and Measuring Women's Empowerment: Literature Review and Future Research Agenda --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Since Kabeer's insightful and influential article in 1999, the research in the field of women studies from the perspectives of women's empowerment has gained immense significance in the academic discourse. This study examines how scholarly research on women's empowerment has evolved over the past two decades by conducting a comprehensive literature analysis. We first compiled the bibliometric data using the Scopus database. The bibliometric data included 916 articles published in 427 peer-reviewed journals by 1,845 authors during 1999-2019, citing the influential work by Kabeer published in the July 1999 issue of the journal - Development and Change. The analysis suggests that research on women's empowerment has primarily been a multi-disciplinary field with journals from diverse disciplines publishing articles on this theme. The analysis identifies the most influential journals, authors, and centres of excellence that have shaped women's empowerment research and unearths the sub-topics related to women's empowerment, which have been in vogue in recent times. The topics trending currently include interrelationships between gender equity and empowerment, measurement of women's empowerment, dimensions, and consequences of women's empowerment. These themes present fresh opportunities for aspiring researchers to align their work in this field. Our analysis makes a significant contribution for researchers interested in women's empowerment by providing a historical perspective, tracing the reason for the spurt in research output, establishing linkages between the articles, and identifying the emerging areas within the broad theme of women's empowerment.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Vibhuti Patel, PhD Professor, Tata Institute of Social Sciences School of Development Studies vibhuti.np@gmail.com Prof. Vibhuti Patel is a distinguished academician, social thinker, researcher and speaker from Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai. She is known for her extensive research and expertise in the issues concerned with women. She has delivered talks on gender issues at several conferences in India and abroad. She is a post-doctoral fellow of London School of Economics and has authored many books, monographs, research papers, commentaries and reviews.</p> <p>Bandana Purkayastha, PhD Professor of Sociology and Asian & Asian American Studies, University of Connecticut bandana.purkayastha@uconn.edu Her research interests focus on gender and intersectionality, migration and migrants, transnationalism, human rights/human security, and violence and peace. She is presently working on projects related gender equity and empowerment in domains of water, higher education and migration</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Editor and Reviewer Comment : Please remove the word 'seminal' from the abstract, then I will be very pleased to</p>

	recommend an accept decision Response from Authors The word 'seminal' has been removed from the abstract.
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Preeti Priya
Professor
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May 25, 2021

Dear Madam,

We had submitted a manuscript entitled “Two decades of Theorising and Measuring Women’s Empowerment: Literature Review and Future Research Agenda” under the category of ‘Review paper’ for consideration by the Women’s Studies International Forum. We are thankful to WSIF for inviting us to resubmit our manuscript after addressing the comment from the editor and reviewer.

We confirm that we have incorporated all the comments appropriately in the revised manuscript. We submit our revision for the kind consideration of the editor.

Sincerely,

Preeti Priya

RESPONSE FROM AUTHORS ON EDITOR AND REVIEWER COMMENTS

Comments from Editor and Reviewer	Response from Authors
<p>Please remove the word 'seminal' from the abstract, then I will be very pleased to recommend an accept decision</p>	<p>The word 'seminal' has been removed from the abstract.</p> <p>Abstract now read as follows:-</p> <p>Since Kabeer's insightful and influential article in 1999, the research in the field of women studies from the perspectives of women's empowerment has gained immense significance in the academic discourse. This study examines how scholarly research on women's empowerment has evolved over the past two decades by conducting a comprehensive literature analysis. We first compiled the bibliometric data using the Scopus database. The bibliometric data included 916 articles published in 427 peer-reviewed journals by 1,845 authors during 1999-2019, citing the influential work by Kabeer published in the July 1999 issue of the journal - Development and Change. The analysis suggests that research on women's empowerment has primarily been a multi-disciplinary field with journals from diverse disciplines publishing articles on this theme. The analysis identifies the most influential journals, authors, and centres of excellence that have shaped women's empowerment research and unearths the sub-topics related to women's empowerment, which have been in vogue in recent times. The topics trending currently include interrelationships between gender equity and empowerment, measurement of women's empowerment, dimensions, and consequences of women's empowerment. These themes present fresh opportunities for aspiring researchers to align their work in this field. Our analysis makes a significant contribution for researchers interested in women's empowerment by providing a historical perspective, tracing the reason for the spurt in research output, establishing linkages between the articles, and identifying the emerging areas within the broad theme of women's empowerment.</p>

HIGHLIGHTS

- Research in women's empowerment has shown a steep rise since 1999 after Kabeer's influential and insightful article that provided a conceptual foundation and explanation for women's empowerment.
- Research on women's empowerment has caught the attention of disciplines as diverse as development studies, gender studies, social sciences, economics, medicine, business management, accounting, and environmental sciences.
- The top 5 journals identified as the most influential journals for research in women's empowerment include World Development, Feminist Economics, Journal of Development Studies, Women's Studies International Forum and Gender and Development.
- The majority of empirical evidence on women's empowerment has been generated from field studies done in Africa and Southeast Asia.
- The potential avenues for future research include measurement issues in women's empowerment, interrelationships between gender equity and empowerment, dimensions of women's empowerment and consequences of women's empowerment.

ABSTRACT

Since Kabeer's insightful and influential article in 1999, the research in the field of women studies from the perspectives of women's empowerment has gained immense significance in the academic discourse. This study examines how scholarly research on women's empowerment has evolved over the past two decades by conducting a comprehensive literature analysis. We first compiled the bibliometric data using the Scopus database. The bibliometric data included 916 articles published in 427 peer-reviewed journals by 1,845 authors during 1999-2019, citing the influential work by Kabeer published in the July 1999 issue of the journal - *Development and Change*. The analysis suggests that research on women's empowerment has primarily been a multi-disciplinary field with journals from diverse disciplines publishing articles on this theme. The analysis identifies the most influential journals, authors, and centres of excellence that have shaped women's empowerment research and unearths the sub-topics related to women's empowerment, which have been in vogue in recent times. The topics trending currently include interrelationships between gender equity and empowerment, measurement of women's empowerment, dimensions, and consequences of women's empowerment. These themes present fresh opportunities for aspiring researchers to align their work in this field. Our analysis makes a significant contribution for researchers interested in women's empowerment by providing a historical perspective, tracing the reason for the spurt in research output, establishing linkages between the articles, and identifying the emerging areas within the broad theme of women's empowerment.

KEYWORDS

1. women's studies
2. women's empowerment
3. gender equity and empowerment
4. literature review
5. bibliometric analysis
6. citation meta-analysis

**Two decades of Theorising and Measuring Women's Empowerment:
Literature Review and Future Research Agenda**

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Two decades of Theorising and Measuring Women's Empowerment: Literature Review and Future Research Agenda

1. Introduction

The last two decades have seen a rapid rise in articles examining women's empowerment, reflecting the significance of this research area in the literature. While we can trace the beginning of this research area in the late 1980s, it gained momentum after Kabeer's influential article that provided a conceptual foundation and explanation for women's empowerment. The theoretical underpinning of her research comes primarily from the writings of Sen(1985) and Batliwala (1993; 1994). Kabeer's framework expanded the notion of empowerment by encompassing the concepts of resource, agency and outcomes.

Since 1999, a plethora of academic research has been published to understand the complexity of the concept of women's empowerment in different socio-cultural contexts across both the developed and developing world. Despite the surge of research on this emerging topic, current work focusing on women's empowerment remains limited and sporadic, and hence a more comprehensive analysis of the literature is required for several reasons. For instance, some studies have theorised the idea of women's empowerment in various domains (Kesby 2005; Mosedale 2005; Sargeson 2008; Choudhury 2009; Bainbridge 2011; Pande, Falle et al. 2011; Whiteside, Tsey et al. 2011; Khader 2012; Galié 2013; Guérin, Kumar et al. 2013; Mosedale 2014; Sen and Mukherjee 2014). Furthermore, some studies have focused on measurement of empowerment (Alkire 2005; Ibrahim and Alkire 2007; Alkire, Meinzen-Dick et al. 2013; Yount, VanderEnde et al. 2016; Cheong, Yount et al. 2017; Miedema, Haardörfer et al. 2018; Galiè, Teufel et al. 2019; Malapit, Quisumbing et al. 2019). Finally, there have been several scholars who have attempted to understand the antecedents and consequences of empowerment(Kabeer 2001; Kabeer 2003; Holvoet 2005; Swain and Wallentin 2009; Rao 2011; Rao 2014; Rao, Vlassoff et al. 2014; Yount, Dijkerman et al. 2014; James-Hawkins, Peters et al. 2018; Galiè, Teufel et al. 2019; Jones, Haardörfer et al. 2019). The extant literature has paid limited attention to examining the breadth and depth of work and has not reflected on how the research has evolved over the last two decades and shaped the research area of women's empowerment. Motivated by the above gaps, this study has attempted to conduct a comprehensive review of the literature analysing citations and content of articles related to women's empowerment published between 1999 and 2019. Firstly, the evolution of research on women's empowerment since 1999 is examined. Then journals, authors, and articles are reviewed to identify the set that has shaped the field of study and is worth reading for future

research in this field. Further to this, key institutions and countries that have contributed substantially to the area of women's empowerment are identified through the analysis of bibliometric data. An in-depth content analysis of the available literature is done to investigate the underlying research streams in the field of women's empowerment that is trending and, thus, needs further attention.

In light of the above, our analysis makes a significant contribution for researchers interested in the field of women's empowerment because it identifies the influential institutions, journals, articles, and authors to be considered when conducting future research on the same theme. It also provides the much-required historical perspective, traces the reason for the spurt in research output, establishes linkages between the articles, and identifies emerging areas within the broad theme of women's empowerment. Thus this review study provides a comprehensive reference guide for researchers and practitioners in the field of women's empowerment.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows; we describe the methodology used in this literature review, followed by our results and discussion. We then present the key trends and essential takeouts in the subsequent section, followed by conclusions. Lastly, we provide our suggestions for researchers interested in this area.

2. Methodology

A bibliometric citation meta-analysis is a standard form of conducting meta-analytical research of literature on a given research topic. The analysis is based on the reasonably justifiable assumption that researchers derive theoretical underpinnings of their research from articles previously published in scholarly journals and publish their findings in similar journals (van Raan 1999; Fetscherin and Heinrich 2015). This kind of review involves a quantitative assessment of literature to bring forth the pivotal articles, authors, institutions, countries, and journals of a given research topic. Additionally, the citation analysis helps the researcher assess the linkages between publications by evaluating their citation and co-citation patterns (Abramo, D'Angelo et al. 2009; Iribarren-Maestro, Lascurain-Sánchez et al. 2009). Metrics, e.g. total citations, average citations received per year, h-index and g-index, are computed in the bibliometric analysis. Such parameters facilitate the measurement of quantum of research and evaluation of their impact in shaping the field (Iribarren-Maestro, Lascurain-Sánchez et al. 2009; Bornmann and Mutz 2015; Rey-Martí, Ribeiro-Soriano et al. 2016; Palomo, Figueroa-Domecq et al. 2017). The bibliometric data being longitudinal helps researchers trace the evolution of a research

topic and identify the trending themes in the literature (De Bakker, Groenewegen et al. 2005). Given the objectives of our study, as outlined in the previous section, bibliometric citation analysis is an appropriate analytical approach.

We collected the bibliographic data from the Scopus database, which contains more than 60 million records across more than 36,000 peer-reviewed titles on varied subject categories. We first searched for the keywords ‘women’s empowerment’, ‘women empowerment’, ‘empowerment of women’ and ‘gender empowerment’. More than 9000 results appeared, of which Naila Kabeer’s work titled “Resources, agency, achievements: Reflections on the measurement of women’s empowerment had the highest citation count of 916 citations in peer-reviewed journal articles. We extracted the bibliometric data of all these 916 articles published during 1999-2019, which referred to Kabeer’s paper (1999). We chose to use the *Bibliometrix* package, which is an R tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. We analysed the bibliometric data and computed specific metrics to categorise the journals, articles, authors, and institutions based on their output and impact. We then visualised the data to understand the citation and co-citation linkages between the published articles, followed by a thorough content analysis of the articles, which helped us identify the underlying research themes.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data analysis, including evaluating the institutions and countries leading in published research regarding women’s empowerment. The study provides an assessment of highly cited and impactful published articles and journals, enabling us to introduce a research agenda in the following section.

We first identified 916 articles referring to Naila Kabeer’s research published in the third issue of the 30th volume of *Development and Change* in 1999. On closer examination, we found that more than 80% of the 916 articles belonged to disciplines of social science (49.3%), arts & humanities (10.0%), economics (9.5%), medicine (8.3%), business management & accounting (5.0%), and environmental science (5%), reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of the research area at first glance.

3.1 Trend in Publication

Research in the field of women’s empowerment has shown a steep rise since 1999, as shown in Figure 1. The increase in publications exhibits associated variation (correlation coefficient – 0.932) with the funding for research in the field of women’s empowerment. While overall, 30%

of 916 published articles received research funding, 100 pieces of 199 articles published in 2019 were funded. Around one-third (32.4%) of supported research received funding from organisations such as United States Agency for International Development (USAID), Department for International Development, UK Government (DFID), Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, and the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC).

Figure 1: Trend in research funding and publication related to women’s empowerment

3.2 Centres of Excellence

To identify the centres of excellence in research on women’s empowerment, we measured the importance of different institutions through the number of articles published in the field of women’s empowerment and their impact in terms of total citations received. The citation score represents the number of times other publications in the Scopus database have cited an article.

Our results show a diverse set of institutions leading this research field. Ten institutions contributed to 29.69% of the total number of articles in this field. The ‘first five’ in terms of the number of publications (P_{WE}) in the area of women’s empowerment include Emory University (USA), Institute of Development Studies (UK), University of California (USA), University of East Anglia (UK), and International Food Policy Research Institute (USA). The University of California tops the list in total citations (1214) received for its 39 published articles. Table 1 provides an overview of the ten most influential institutions involved in the research on women’s empowerment in terms of the number of articles published (left side of the table) and the number of citations received from their publications (right side of the table).

The University of Sussex (UK), Columbia University (USA), and London School of Economics are the three new institutions feature in the list based on total citations received. These institutions should be considered 'centres of excellence ' in the context of women's empowerment research. This analysis helps researchers target institutions for potential collaboration.

Table 1: Most Influential Institutions [sorted by P_{WE} (left) and TC (right)]

Rank	Institutions	P _{WE}	TC	C/P _{WE}	Rank	Institutions	P _{WE}	TC	C/P _{WE}
1	<i>Emory University</i>	63	808	13	1	<i>University of California</i>	39	1214	31
2	<i>Institute of Development Studies</i>	63	430	7	2	<i>Emory University</i>	63	808	13
3	<i>University of California</i>	39	1214	31	3	<i>International Food Policy Research Institute</i>	34	705	21
4	<i>International Food Policy Research Institute</i>	34	705	21	4	<i>University of Sussex</i>	11	620	56
5	<i>University of East Anglia</i>	18	281	16	5	<i>Institute of Development Studies</i>	63	430	7
6	<i>International Centre for Research on Women</i>	17	259	15	6	<i>University of London</i>	12	415	35
7	<i>London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine</i>	13	319	25	7	<i>Columbia University</i>	8	373	47
8	<i>University of Aberdeen</i>	13	297	23	8	<i>London School of Economics</i>	8	333	42
9	<i>University of London</i>	12	415	35	9	<i>London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine</i>	13	319	25
10	<i>Saint Mary's University</i>	12	257	21	10	<i>University of Sheffield</i>	10	304	30

Note:

P_{WE}: Number of published articles related to the field of women's empowerment

TC: Total citations received

C/P_{WE}: Citations per published paper (P_{WE}/TC)

Figure 2 presents the top ten countries in terms of the number of articles published by authors affiliated to an institution located in a country. Researchers from the USA and UK have contributed to more than one-fifth of total research output in the area of women’s empowerment. Figure 2 also provides the bifurcation of published papers into single-country and multi-country publications. The country rankings reflect where the ‘centres of excellence’ are present.

Figure 2: Ranking of top 10 countries (sorted by the number of papers)

3.3 Most Influential Journals

Researchers use bibliometric citation analysis to assess journals’ performance (Abramo, D’Angelo et al. 2009; Fetscherin and Heinrich 2015; Palomo, Figueroa-Domecq et al. 2017). We wished to identify the journals that have ‘shaped’ the field of research on women’s empowerment on the dimensions of ‘output’ and ‘impact.’ A total of 427 journals have published articles related to women’s empowerment during the last two decades. Of these, 37 journals have published at least five articles over the previous two decades, contributing to 41% of total publications in the field of women’s empowerment. Table 2 summarises the top 20 journals in terms of the total number of articles published related to women’s empowerment and their impact measured by the average citations received per year. The top five journals are *World Development*, *Feminist Economics*, *Journal of Development Studies*, *Women’s Studies International*

Forum and Gender and Development. Overall, social science journals, specifically those focusing on the broad field of development, and journals that have a specific focus on women's issues, dominate the list of most influential journals.

Table2: Ranking of top 20 journals (sorted by P_{WE})

Source	Label	P_{WE}	h-index	TC	TC/t
1. <i>World Development</i>	WD	49	18	1620	85.26
2. <i>Feminist Economics</i>	FE	25	10	332	19.53
3. <i>Journal of Development Studies</i>	JDS	23	9	448	23.58
4. <i>Women's Studies International Forum</i>	WSIF	19	5	121	7.12
5. <i>Gender and Development</i>	GAD	15	8	585	39.00
6. <i>Social Indicators Research</i>	SIR	15	6	219	14.60
7. <i>Development in Practice</i>	DP	15	4	62	3.65
8. <i>Social Science and Medicine</i>	SSAM	12	9	525	37.50
9. <i>Journal of Human Development and Capabilities</i>	JHDC	12	3	58	9.67
10. <i>Gender, Place and Culture</i>	GPC	12	6	133	6.65
11. <i>Gender, Technology and Development</i>	GTD	12	5	58	4.14
12. <i>Development and Change</i>	DC	10	7	424	23.56
13. <i>Journal of International Development</i>	JID	10	6	341	22.73
14. <i>International Journal of Educational Development</i>	IJED	10	5	194	12.93
15. <i>Culture, Health and Sexuality</i>	CHS	10	3	35	3.89
16. <i>BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth</i>	BMCPCB	9	4	112	11.20
17. <i>Global Public Health</i>	GPH	8	6	108	18.00
18. <i>Maternal and Child Nutrition</i>	MCN	7	3	107	21.40
19. <i>PLOS One</i>	PO	7	3	58	9.67
20. <i>Asian Journal of Women's Studies</i>	AJWS	7	1	7	0.70

To further investigate the results, we analysed 37 journals that published at least five articles. We considered the number of articles (P_{WE}) published as a proxy of output and the average citations received per year (TC/t) as a proxy for the impact on women's empowerment research. Figure 3 illustrates a quadrant analysis, where the horizontal axis represents the number of articles published in journals and the vertical axis represents the average citations received per year by the journals. We evaluated the mean values of both the variables (Mean of $P_{WE} = 10.2$ and Mean of TC/t=12.4) and identified four main groups of journals. Quadrant A consists of high output and high impact, quadrant B: low output and high impact, quadrant C: high output and little impact and quadrant D: low output and low impact. There are only six journals in the quadrant A, which means these journals have performed well on both quantity

and quality. These six journals are *World Development*, *Gender and Development*, *Social Science and Medicine*, *Journal of Development Studies*, *Feminist Economics and Social Indicators Research* as can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Journal Focus and Impact on Women's Empowerment Research

While Figure 3 presents the big picture of the influential journals, we provide more details to the readers through Figure 4, which shows the position of 31 journals otherwise located in the quadrants B, C, and D in Figure 3. As presented in Figure 4, this two-dimensional map identifies the second most influential group of journals for researchers to find a potential outlet for disseminating their research in the field of women's empowerment. This group of journals include *Social Science and Medicine*, *Development and Change*, *Journal of International Development*, *International Journal of Educational Development*, *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities* and *BMC Pregnancy and Child Birth*.

As part of the research, our main interest was in assessing the most influential journals but not in identifying every outlet of research in women's empowerment. Hence, we chose not to analyse this further and addressed our next question to identifying the authors and articles being worth reading to conduct future research in this field.

Figure 4: Journal Focus and Impact on Women's Empowerment Research (detailed view)

3.4 Most Influential Authors

A total of 1845 researchers have contributed to the area of women’s empowerment research during the last two decades. Most researchers (462) have not received a single citation for their publication. There are 25 authors whose paper(s) have received at least 150 citations, and we identify them as influential authors. We have provided a list of top 10 authors based on the number of papers (left) and the number of citations (right) in Table 3. The two rankings are starkly different with only two authors; Quisumbing and KM Yount being common to both the lists. While KM Yount has published the maximum number of articles, Naila Kabeer herself has been the most impactful author in the field of women’s research during the last two decades. It is also interesting to note that 16 out of 18 top authors listed in Table 3 are women researchers primarily from institutions located in the US and UK. This analysis is useful for researchers wishing to target authors worth reading to understand the body of literature available on women’s empowerment research and to identify the potential collaborators in the field.

Table 3: Most Influential Authors [sorted by P_{WE} (left) and TC (right)]

Author	P _{WE}	TC	h-Index	TC/P _{WE}	Author	P _{WE}	TC	h-Index	TC/P _{WE}
Yount K M	32	391	13	12.2	Kabeer N	4	982	4	245.5
Cheong Y F	9	76	5	8.4	Alkire S	3	421	3	140.3
Quisumbing A	7	418	3	59.7	Quisumbing A	7	418	3	59.7
Rao N	6	56	4	9.3	Yount K M	32	391	13	12.2
Pandey S	6	29	3	4.8	Kesby M	2	304	2	152.0
James Hawkins L	6	24	2	4.0	Molyneux M	2	280	2	140.0
Grabe S	5	108	4	21.6	Luke N	1	259	1	259.0
Cunningham K	5	169	3	33.8	Malapit HJ	5	255	1	51.0
Gali A	5	25	3	5.0	Salway S	2	250	2	125.0
Miedema SS	5	31	3	6.2	Krishnan S	4	243	4	60.8

3.5 Research Sub-Themes

We analysed the co-occurrence of keywords and co-citation of articles to identify the research streams because keywords represent the content of the article. In all, there were 1866 keywords, out of which 104 keywords registered more than five occurrences. We computed the number of occurrences, links (number of co-occurrences of a keyword with other keywords), and total link strength (number of publications in which two keywords occur together) of keywords and sorted them in the descending order of their overall link strength. We listed the top 30 keywords in Table 4; the term ‘empowerment’ figured with the highest strength of 209, followed by ‘women’s empowerment’.

Table 4: Important Keywords (sorted on Total Link Strength)

Rank	Keyword	Occurrences	Total Link Strength
1	Empowerment	167	209
2	Gender	159	195
3	Women	77	110
4	Women's empowerment	91	105
5	Agency	71	94
6	India	62	86
7	Bangladesh	34	58
8	Development	29	43
9	Agriculture	21	42
10	Microfinance	23	39
11	South asia	19	35
12	Education	19	34
13	Measurement	14	28
14	Participation	16	27
15	Autonomy	12	26
16	Microcredit	11	25
17	Nutrition	9	25

While keywords' analysis allowed us to provide readers with a general idea of the content of published research in women's empowerment, we computed the direct citation linkages among the published articles in the dataset. Aiming to identify the core structure of the women's empowerment research, we analysed articles with more than 18 citations, which is the average citation of a published article in the database, leaving 163 papers, i.e. 17.7% of the publications. Then we chose articles that had at least two links leading us to 48 papers for constructing the article network and visualising how the articles have been co-cited. We have presented the citation network as constructed aided by VOS Viewer in Figure 6. The node in the figure represents an article. The citation link between the two articles is established if both contain commonly cited references.

Figure 6: Citation mapping of women's empowerment research

Next, we conducted a content analysis of these 48 papers and identified eight distinct but interrelated themes in women's empowerment research. These streams are: (i) Concept development of gender equality and women's empowerment (Kabeer 2005; Kesby 2005), (ii) Empirical evidence on the role of microfinance on women's empowerment (Kabeer 2001; Holvoet 2005; Garikipati 2008; Grabe 2010), (iii) Community mobilisation and women's empowerment (Mosedale 2005; Jakimow and Kilby 2006; Blanchard, Mohan et al. 2013; Beattie, Mohan et al. 2014; Haugh and Talwar 2016), (iv) Development of quantitative indicators (Alkire 2005; Ibrahim and Alkire 2007; Wyndow, Li et al. 2013; Trommlerová, Klasen et al. 2015; Pratley 2016), (v) Women's empowerment in agriculture (Alkire, Meinzen-Dick et al. 2013;

Sraboni, Malapit et al. 2014; Cunningham, Ploubidis et al. 2015; Cunningham, Ruel et al. 2015; Malapit, Kadiyala et al. 2015; Anderson, Reynolds et al. 2017), (vi) Women’s empowerment and child nutrition (Furuta and Salway 2006; Acharya, Bell et al. 2010; Mabsout and van Staveren 2010), (vii) Women’s empowerment and reproductive healthcare (Allendorf 2007; Mumtaz and Salway 2009; Carlson, Kordas et al. 2015; Osamor and Grady 2016), (viii) Determinants of women’s empowerment (Kantor 2003; Rahman and Rao 2004; Yount 2005; Anderson and Eswaran 2009; Yount, VanderEnde et al. 2016).

3.6 Most influential articles and trending papers

Of the 916 papers studied, 28 articles had more than 100 citations, 669 had less than 100 citations, while 220 papers have not been cited yet. We followed a multi-step process to identify the most impactful articles and authors in the field. We first assessed the impact of the published articles in total citations received and average citations per year. We present the results of this procedure in Table 5. The rankings indicate that these ten articles may be considered highly influential in shaping women’s empowerment further. Most of these papers have deepened the understanding of women’s empowerment primarily by examining the condition and positions of women empirically as a consequence of specific development interventions (Luke 2003; Kabeer 2005; Furuta and Salway 2006; Molyneux 2006; Kabeer 2009), by developing the theory of women’s empowerment (Kesby 2005; Chant 2008; Anderson and Eswaran 2009), and by designing a scheme of measuring women’s empowerment (Ibrahim and Alkire 2007; Alkire, Meinzen-Dick et al. 2013). The countries studied in these research papers belong to developing countries from South Asia, Latin America, and Africa. These impactful articles have been published in journals committed to the broad field of development research, e.g. *Journal of Development Studies*, *World Development*, *Oxford Development Studies*, *Social Policy & Administration*, and *Journal of Development Economics*.

Table 5: Ranking of top 10 articles (sorted by total citations)

Rank	Article	TC	TC/t
1	Kabeer, N. (2005). "Gender equality and women's empowerment: A critical analysis of the third millennium development goal 1." <i>Gender & Development</i> 13 (1): 13-24.	443	29.53
2	Kabeer, N. (2009). Conflicts over credit: re-evaluating the empowerment potential of loans to women in rural Bangladesh. <i>Microfinance</i> , Routledge: 128-162.	424	22.32
3	Molyneux, M. (2006). "Mothers at the service of the new poverty agenda: progresas/oportunidades, Mexico's conditional transfer programme." <i>Social Policy & Administration</i> 40 (4): 425-449.	264	18.86

4	Luke, N. (2003). "Age and economic asymmetries in the sexual relationships of adolescent girls in sub-Saharan Africa." <u>Studies in family planning</u> 34 (2): 67-86.	259	15.24
5	Kesby, M. (2005). "Rethorizing empowerment-through-participation as a performance in space: Beyond tyranny to transformation." <u>Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society</u> 30 (4): 2037-2065.	195	13.00
6	Furuta, M. and S. Salway (2006). "Women's position within the household as a determinant of maternal health care use in Nepal." <u>International family planning perspectives</u> : 17-27.	176	12.57
7	Chant, S. (2008). "The 'feminisation of poverty' and the 'feminisation' of anti-poverty programmes: Room for revision?" <u>The Journal of Development Studies</u> 44 (2): 165-197.	172	14.33
8	Alkire, S., R. Meinzen-Dick, et al. (2013). "The women's empowerment in agriculture index." <u>World Development</u> 52 : 71-91.	160	22.86
9	Ibrahim, S. and S. Alkire (2007). "Agency and empowerment: A proposal for internationally comparable indicators." <u>Oxford development studies</u> 35 (4): 379-403.	148	11.38
10	Anderson, S. and M. Eswaran (2009). "What determines female autonomy? Evidence from Bangladesh." <u>Journal of Development Economics</u> 90 (2): 179-191.	146	13.27

Note:

TC: Total Citations

TC/t: Average citations received per year since the year of publication

Identifying the roots of women's empowerment research is a practical action, and hence we attempted to determine where these articles are heading. We analysed if the influential articles had acquired more citations at the end of the period studied- 2019 in our case.

Table 6: Ranking of Top 20 articles (sorted by RC_{End})

Ran k	Article	TC	TC (First 5 Yrs)	TC (Last 5 Yrs)	RC _{End}
1	Kabeer, N. (2005). "Gender equality and women's empowerment: A critical analysis of the third millennium development goal 1." <u>Gender & Development</u> 13 (1): 13-24.	443	10	314	31.40
2	Ibrahim, S. and S. Alkire (2007). "Agency and empowerment: A proposal for internationally comparable indicators." <u>Oxford development studies</u> 35 (4): 379-403.	148	11	104	9.45
3	Rahman, L. and V. Rao (2004). "The determinants of gender equity in India: examining Dyson and Moore's thesis with new data." <u>Population and Development Review</u> 30 (2): 239-268.	116	9	59	6.56
4	Kabeer, N. (2009). Conflicts over credit: re-evaluating the empowerment potential of loans to women in rural Bangladesh. <u>Microfinance</u> , Routledge: 128-162.	424	38	206	5.42
5	Anderson, S. and M. Eswaran (2009). "What determines female autonomy? Evidence from Bangladesh." <u>Journal of Development Economics</u> 90 (2): 179-191.	146	21	109	5.19

6	Garikipati, S. (2008). "The impact of lending to women on household vulnerability and women's empowerment: evidence from India." <u>World development</u> 36 (12): 2620-2642.	141	19	94	4.95
7	Mosedale, S. (2005). "Assessing women's empowerment: towards a conceptual framework." <u>Journal of International Development</u> 17 (2): 243-257.	134	13	60	4.62
8	Chant, S. (2008). "The 'feminisation of poverty' and the 'feminisation' of anti-poverty programmes: Room for revision?" <u>The Journal of Development Studies</u> 44 (2): 165-197.	172	27	106	3.93
9	Batterbury, S. (2001). "Landscapes of diversity: a local political ecology of livelihood diversification in south-western Niger." <u>Ecumene</u> 8 (4): 437-464.	110	10	39	3.90
10	Luke, N. (2003). "Age and economic asymmetries in the sexual relationships of adolescent girls in sub-Saharan Africa." <u>Studies in family planning</u> 34 (2): 67-86.	259	28	105	3.75
11	Furuta, M. and S. Salway (2006). "Women's position within the household as a determinant of maternal health care use in Nepal." <u>International family planning perspectives</u> : 17-27.	176	26	97	3.73
12	Alkire, S. (2005). "Subjective quantitative studies of human agency." <u>Social indicators research</u> 74 (1): 217-260.	113	18	67	3.72
13	Holvoet, N. (2005). "The impact of microfinance on decision-making agency: evidence from South India." <u>Development and Change</u> 36 (1): 75-102.	110	13	44	3.38
14	Kilby, P. (2006). "Accountability for empowerment: Dilemmas facing non-governmental organisations." <u>World Development</u> 34 (6): 951-963.	127	22	63	2.86
15	Kesby, M. (2005). "Rethorizing empowerment-through-participation as a performance in space: Beyond tyranny to transformation." <u>Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society</u> 30 (4): 2037-2065.	195	41	80	1.95
16	Molyneux, M. (2006). "Mothers at the service of the new poverty agenda: progres/a/oportunidades, Mexico's conditional transfer programme." <u>Social Policy & Administration</u> 40 (4): 425-449.	264	61	115	1.89
17	Rocca, C. H., S. Rathod, et al. (2008). "Challenging assumptions about women's empowerment: social and economic resources and domestic violence among young married women in urban South India." <u>International Journal of Epidemiology</u> 38 (2): 577-585.	115	37	67	1.81
18	Kesby, M. (2007). "Spatialising participatory approaches: the contribution of geography to a mature debate." <u>Environment and Planning A</u> 39 (12): 2813-2831.	109	32	43	1.34
19	Swendeman, D., I. Basu, et al. (2009). "Empowering sex workers in India to reduce vulnerability to HIV and sexually transmitted diseases." <u>Social science & medicine</u> 69 (8): 1157-1166.	124	44	45	1.02
20	Dworkin, S. L. and A. A. Ehrhardt (2007). "Going beyond "ABC" to include "GEM": critical reflections on progress in the HIV/AIDS epidemic." <u>American journal of public health</u> 97 (1): 13-18.	121	56	29	0.52

Note:

TC: Total citations received

$TC_{(First\ 5\ Yrs)}$: Total citations received during the first five years of publication

$TC_{(Last\ 5\ Yrs)}$: Total citations received during the last five years of publication

RC_{End} : $TC_{(last\ 5\ Yrs)}/TC_{(First\ 5\ Yrs)}$

This analysis helped us not only to identify the papers that were cited over a fixed period but also if those papers were cited more recently, allowing us to identify, thereby, emerging topics in the field. We computed the ratio of citations in the end (RC_{End}) by dividing the citations received in the last five years by the citations received in the first five years of a publication—higher the ratio, the more trending the paper. We listed the articles sorted by their RC_{End} in Table 6. A close look at the table indicates four streams of research trending in the field: (i) interrelationship between gender equity and women’s empowerment, (ii) measurement of women’s empowerment, (iii) determinants of women’s empowerment and (iv) consequence of women’s empowerment. This analysis is useful for researchers who wish to choose the topic(s) for their research in women’s empowerment. The next section discusses the analyses of keywords defined by authors in their respective articles and co-citations of papers in the studied database.

4. Conclusion

We have endeavoured to provide a roadmap for researchers in the field of women’s empowerment. The paper by Kabeer (1999) proved to be the inflexion point for the take-off on research on women’s empowerment. It is pertinent to mention here that while insightful research on women’s empowerment had occurred before Kabeer (1999), the latter has undoubtedly provided the impetus for further investigation. It is heartening to note that women’s empowerment has caught the attention of disciplines as diverse as development studies, gender studies, social sciences, economics, medicine, accounting, and environmental sciences. This broad diversity in subject implies that researchers are increasingly approaching problems in their field through the gender lens. The steady rise in research in this field has been possible due to financial support from international development funding agencies like USAID, Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, DFID, and ESRC. A country-wise analysis of research in women’s empowerment indicates that developing countries such as India and Bangladesh figure in the top ten countries as far as the number of published papers is concerned. Additionally, we found the institutions and universities that can be approached for collaborations and guidance by new researchers in this field.

The analysis of journals influential in research on women's empowerment reveals that it is primarily the journals in gender, social sciences, and development studies that have exerted the maximum influence. If one were to isolate a single journal for having wielded the maximum impact in this field during the last two decades, it would be *World Development* because of the number of impactful papers published by the same.

Our analysis unearthed the sub-topics related to women's empowerment which have been in vogue in recent times. The topics trending currently include interrelationships between gender equity and empowerment, measurement issues in women's empowerment, determinants of drivers of women's empowerment, and consequences of women's empowerment. These themes present fresh opportunities for aspiring researchers to align their work in this field. Amongst the trending themes, research on developing quantitative indicators to measure empowerment is gaining the maximum attention. A further systematic review of the literature would be advantageous to understand the theoretical, contextual and methodological gaps in the measurement of women's empowerment.

Despite being highly objective, we would be the first to identify some potential limitations in the study. We have applied a priori yardsticks of inclusion and exclusion of research articles that could be subjects of inadvertent biases despite our best efforts. Only articles indexed in Scopus were selected, and hence there are chances of some being left out if they are not yet indexed to the database. Also, if not written in English, particularly from countries like India and Bangladesh, articles could contain rich insights but have not been considered in this bibliometric analysis.

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